

A Review Of The Cultural Changes And Inheritance Of Short-Arm Wushu In China

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<p><i>Chinese martial arts short-arm is an important part of Chinese martial arts, which is a modern sport item after the competition of Chinese martial arts sword technique. This article mainly uses the literature material, the comprehensive analysis method carries on the combing to the Chinese and foreign regarding the short-arm development academic history, the discovery: The sport of fencing, one of the modern skirmishes, dates back to Ancient Egypt, originated in Spain, was perfected in Italy, and flourished in France. Its popularity is due to the "Chivalry" in the western sports thought, and in the improvement of the sword, the improvement of protective equipment with innovative thinking, so that in today's world has a relatively systematic operating system, by the overwhelming majority of people in pursuit. There are many researches on the bare-handed exercises of wushu equipment in China, such as the origin of history and culture, the beauty of wushu equipment, the collation of history, the analysis and comparison of project techniques, etc. , there is no complete and detailed explanation of the equipment-based combat items, and there is even a lack of promotion and sorting of Chinese short-range military equipment as a whole. Instead, it is mostly explained from a single category of items, there is a lack of in-depth discussion on the difficulties and solutions faced by the development of equipment-based fighting projects. Secondly, in recent years, with the national attention to martial arts culture, the study of Chinese short-arm project began to revive, research mainly from the project techniques, project promotion and other issues, however, it does not analyze the problems in the promotion of short-arm in China China short-arm competition form is not unified, the project equipment is easy to wear out, clothing, protective equipment is not determined, equipment and techniques are not unified in-depth analysis and mining. Furthermore, the study of Chinese martial arts is to make it continue to play an important role in the contemporary society of moral norms and value guidance, that is, to achieve the Chinese martial arts martial arts martial arts culture inheritance and development.</i></p>
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Introduction

Chinese Wushu Bing Dao is an important part of Chinese Wushu culture and a confrontational sport developed by the excellent Chinese nation in its long-term historical development and social practice. In 2019, the Wushu Industry Development Plan (2019-2025), jointly issued by the State General Administration of Sports, the Ministry of Education and other departments, encourages the establishment of a comprehensive national list of key Wushu projects and the establishment of four major columns to cultivate. In response to the national and social demands for cultural confidence, the Chinese martial arts short arms are listed as one of the items to be vigorously developed, which ushers in a policy "spring breeze" for the development of the Chinese martial arts short arms.

Therefore, through combing the formation, development and inheritance changes of Chinese Wushu Bingdao Chinese Wushu Shorty, analyzing many problems and contradictions in the process of cultural reproduction, according to the new opportunities and new trends in the development of Chinese Wushu Bingdao Chinese Wushu Shorty today, and combining the fitness needs of the people, this study positions the value of Chinese Wushu Shorty culture from a new perspective, so as to build the content system, competition system and cultural system of Chinese Wushu Shorty in the new era. In this way, the content system, competition system, and cultural system of Chinese martial arts will be constructed in the new era, and through adaptation or transformation, it will be able to complete modern reconstruction and benign operation, and become a significant local iconic symbol of China again. It is hoped that this will serve to promote the coordinated development of Chinese martial arts short arms programs with all aspects of current Chinese society and economy, promote the sustainable development of Chinese martial arts short arms programs, meet the current

needs of the masses for diversified fitness and social development, and promote the development of Chinese martial arts Bing Dao to a higher level.

Academic history and research dynamics of relevant foreign studies

Western research on traditional Chinese culture began as early as the middle of the 16th century, especially in the category of weapons, focusing on ancient and modern military uses. The culture of weaponry and its martial education in Japan and Korea were deeply influenced by the development of martial arts weaponry in China, and many writings of warriors emerged. Spain, Italy, France, and other Western countries are known for their fencing sports among their short weapons programs.

Related studies of Japanese kendo

The historical text "History of the Military System of Sui and Tang Dynasty" records that since the period of Chinese Emperor Wu of Han Dynasty, Japan sent ambassadors to have frequent good relations with the Han court and frequent exchanges with Chinese civil merchants, such as swords, spears, mace and other Chinese short weapons instruments, techniques and "Sun Tzu's Art of War" and other military science and theory were also introduced to Japan in large quantities through the Korean state. Japanese warriors learned and improved on the basis of ancient Chinese sword forms, manufacturing techniques and technology in the years of constant military warfare, and Japanese sword forms and techniques with Japanese style were basically formed in the middle and late Muromachi period. The Japanese sword and swordsmanship became more concise and practical, and the technology and techniques of weapon making gradually matured. The Japanese sword was shaped like a small curved moon, with a narrow body and a sharp blade, which made the Japanese sword and swordsmanship more ferocious. At the same time, the political rights and social status of Japanese samurai were also very high. Especially in Japan Nara era (China Tang dynasty period), Japan from the clan, down to the people, deeply influenced by Confucius Confucian education, coupled with the Meiji emperor of Japan before the reign, the people of society are managed and ruled by the Japanese samurai class, Japanese society, the style of martial arts is prevalent, and even produced a special kendo master and kendo teacher model. In the course of the changing times, the emergence of bamboo swords and protective gear eliminated the long-used wooden swords and made practical "striking" training possible. During the Taisho period (the first part of the nineteenth century), the Japanese sword and swordsmanship evolved through actual combat, and the many sword schools in Japan were unified and organized to form the "Japanese Kendo", which was free from the shackles of the Chinese sword and swordsmanship. From the Taisho to the early Showa period (the first and middle of the nineteenth century), the unification of Japanese kendo was completed, and a more complete "kendo" system was formed and popularized among civilians and the government military. In addition, Japanese kendo was based on the traditional Chinese rituals of Confucianism and Zen Buddhism, which were directly transposed into the moral values of the Japanese samurai. In the Meiji years, the Western-style education system of "education for the nation" was introduced, and kendo was officially established as a formal curriculum in Japanese high schools and teacher training schools. Hidemaki Kinoshita and Qu Yang (2000), in "From Art to Way: The Modern Development of Budo," document the origins of the "Bushido" spirit of Japanese kendo from 1906 to 1913. In 1931, kendo and judo were made part of the Japanese national curriculum, a compulsory course for secondary school and teacher training boys. After the Russo-Japanese War, Japan switched from bamboo sword competition to the resurrection of kendo, and in 1958, the "fighting techniques" of Japanese kendo came on the scene, and there was a problem of "from technique to path". Since then, the term "kendo" was established, the technical system of kendo was formally formed, and sports tournaments of kendo were frequently held in Japan, and Japanese kendo began to develop rapidly as a sport. In the 1970s, Japanese kendo became not only popular in Japan, but also in Southeast Asia, Europe and America, and its techniques were changing rapidly. In the course of its development, Japanese kendo established a relatively complete set of rules for competition. The individual tournament and team tournament are the main ones, with the individual tournament using two wins in three battles and the team tournament consisting of a points competition and an elimination tournament. The format, the system and how to calculate the scores are also specified in detail.

Along with the rise and fall of the Japanese nation, Japanese kendo has followed the traditional Eastern way of thinking and also incorporated advanced Western sporting concepts, transforming to form a line of development of both traditional and creative forms of competition. In "The Historical Evolution of Japanese Kendo", Nie Xiaohu mentions that Japanese kendo has developed a distinctive Japanese culture and national humanistic values during its long history of evolution. Along with social change and development, Japanese kendo has incorporated various cultures and Confucianism, making it a symbol of spirituality and culture. Chen Yongjun (2001), as well as Qin Gang, have discussed the spirit and ideas embedded in kendo. For example, Chen Yongjun argues that Japanese kendo is synonymous with martial arts, with Zen thought as the main thread, and that the aim is to get rid of evil rather than kill. It is thus clear that Japanese kendo contains not only technical and tactical training, but also the educational ideas of Chinese Confucianism. In "The Inspiration of Japanese Kendo to Traditional Chinese Martial Arts", it is argued that the so-called "Kendo" is the fusion of "sword" and

"Tao", the fusion of technique and spirit. It cannot be used only for practice and fitness, but should be explored in depth for its cultural connotation. This also gives us a reference for the development of the Chinese martial art of Budo, which should be developed and popularized as a school sports program.

It can be seen that the rapid development of Japanese kendo is inseparable from its cultural connotation, national spirit and etiquette norms. This spirit of pursuing the ultimate and forward-looking vision of development and inheritance contributed to the development of Japanese kendo so rapidly.

Research on overseas fencing

The history of fencing can be traced back as far as 3,000 years ago, to ancient Egypt in 1190 BC. In ancient times, "swords" were used mainly for killing in war and training soldiers. Spain is considered the cradle of modern fencing, and by the end of the 14th century, with the development of weapons, the sword was losing its place in the military, so fencing was retained as a form of physical fitness and dueling recreation. In the 17th century, the French made further improvements to the sword, making it shorter and lighter for offense and defense, and making fencing faster and more technical. technology was introduced to Italy, and the Italians invented the modern saber. Fencing was established at the first Olympic Games in Athens in 1896, and has since become a traditional competitive sport in all Olympic Games. The International Fencing Federation was founded on November 29, 1913 in Paris, France. The following year, the adoption of the Fencing Competition Rules put fencing on a fair and rational path.

It can be seen that fencing, one of the modern short arms, dates back to ancient Egypt, was created in Spain, perfected in Italy, and flourished in France. Fencing has become widespread thanks to the "chivalry" of Western sporting thought and innovative thinking in the improvement of swords and protective gear, to the point that it has become a relatively systematic system of operation worldwide and is highly sought after by most people today.

In summary, about the overview of the Japanese kendo, Western fencing and other foreign short weapon research results, for our comprehensive, internal and external overall understanding of the development of Chinese martial arts weapon way Chinese martial arts short weapon has important reference significance.

Second, the academic history of domestic related research combing and research dynamics

Chinese martial arts culture is profound and profound, and there are many kinds of items involved, and there are rich researches on popular martial arts sports, such as martial arts routines, combat confrontation, equipment and traditional health care, for example, research on martial arts routines, research on taijiquan and research on fitness qigong. Searching for "Chinese sword fighting" through academic websites such as Zhiwang, there are 37 core journals and 77 master's theses; while searching for "Chinese short armament", there are only 4 core journals and 6 master's theses; searching for "martial arts short armament The search for "Chinese short armament" showed only 9 core journals, 4 of which were duplicates of "Chinese short armament", and 19 master's theses; while the search for the term "the way of armament" showed 14 core journals, all of which presented studies of drama, opera literature, fiction, and social science. If we searched for the term "Chinese martial arts and the way of war", we found that the research on the culture of Chinese martial arts and the way of war is even more difficult to find, which may be due to the inconsistent definition of the concept. Therefore, our search revealed that studies on "short military" are mostly scattered and lack an overall unification from the theoretical level of the literature. Therefore, the following review intends to take Chinese swordsmanship as a breakthrough in the literature of Chinese martial arts short instruments such as knives, swords, and sticks, based on Chinese martial arts swords, and to unify them from the literature on Chinese martial arts short instruments or ancient Chinese swordsmanship, and on this basis, we will again conduct the academic history of Chinese martial arts short weapons.

Research on Chinese martial arts short instruments

There are many different kinds of Chinese martial arts instruments, and the short apparatus competitions, which started to be developed in 1979 and are still in the experimental stage, have been called "short weapons". In 1928, when the first national examination of the Chinese martial arts was held, which focused on techniques rather than routines, the term "swords and sabers" was used, but the term was not yet adopted. In 1931, the "Rules of the National Martial Arts Competition" directly adopted the title of "fencing"; in 1933, the second National Martial Arts Examination was held, and at that time, although the terms The descriptions of "long weapons" and "short weapons" appeared at this time, but they were not the long weapons or short weapons in the Chinese martial art of Bing Dao that we talk about today, but referred to the two categories of stick and gun, sword and knife respectively.

Related research on Chinese martial arts sword and knife instruments

Zhong Shaoyi (1994) introduced the historical origin and characteristics of the ancient Chinese sword fighting technique, which led to the study of the ancient sword fighting technique in martial arts. Shen Zhiping, Guo Guojin (1998) explored the formation of the sword, the development and evolution of the ancient sword and

sword art separately from the perspective of historiography. Zheng Ruiman (2002) explores the cause of the Dao and the sword in ancient literature from a literary perspective, showing that the Daoist philosophy of "nothing is the Dao" is connected with the feminine, subtle, and fluid sword meaning, and thus ancient sword literature often uses the sword as a metaphor for the Dao. Zhao Guoqing (2003), in his study of Chinese fencing culture and today's fencing routines, argues that fencing routines must reflect the techniques and "strength," "speed," "speed," "speed," "speed," "speed," "speed," "speed," and "speed." He believes that the development of Chinese swordsmanship must be improved and enhanced in terms of technique and power. Weng Shixun (2004), in his study of the "Yue Nün (Yue Women) on Swordplay", insists on the "humanistic supremacy" viewpoint in order to develop Chinese national sports such as swordplay and other short apparatus items. Luo Liqun (2007) explores the cultural traits of ancient Chinese swordsmen from a literary perspective and concludes that ancient Chinese society had a strong culture of sword worship, which flourished in the Tang Dynasty and reached its glory in the Qing Dynasty. Guo Des (2007) summarizes Ma Mingda's Sword Talking Series, concluding that the scholarly collection focuses on the history of martial arts, and from the perspective of cultural history, it analyzes various ancient Chinese weapons, the emergence, transmission, and evolution of Chinese martial arts techniques, and elaborates on the humanistic sentiments and cultural implications unique to the Chinese martial art of the Way of the Sword. Qiu Suibing and Gao Ying (2008) conducted an experimental analysis of taijiquan training and knife training for college students and showed that the multiple intelligences training method was more effective than the traditional training method in improving physical motor intelligence and spatial intelligence. Lin Xianliang (2009) traces the relationship between sword and chivalry from a literary perspective. He argues that martial arts received the attention of the ruling class during the Tang Dynasty due to the intermingling of the Hu and Han peoples, which led to the formation of a culture of martial arts and chivalry, and thus led to more people practicing martial arts. Dai Guobin (2009) analyzes and interprets the use of the sword, its role, techniques and cultural imagery from a historical and cultural perspective. He Tianjin and Ma Li (2010) discuss the beauty of movement and form in Chinese swordplay in the context of film and television, and the "mood", "rhythm", "resemblance", and The "mood", "rhythm", "resemblance", and "spirit" of the Chinese sword are often combined with the sword wielder to shape the soul of the sword art. Luo Shiming (2011) studied the historical footprint of Chinese martial arts and concluded that the original source of martial arts was the fighting skills of primitive human societies, while the ancient martial arts were the direct offspring of the parent of Chinese martial arts, which are distinctly different. In a study of ancient Chinese military sports, Zhang Jing and Huang Yafei (2009) showed that swordplay was a weapon used militarily for close combat and self-defense in ancient China, starting in the late Western Zhou Dynasty and flourishing in the Spring and Autumn and Warring States. Among them, the swords of Wu and Yue were known for their sharpness and delicacy, and famous sword makers such as Ganzhong, Mo Xie, and Ou Ye Zi emerged. Zhang Jun (2011) studied the evolution of swords in the Han dynasty, the early Han dynasty was mainly used in the military, the sword body was doubled in length on the basis of the swords in the Spring and Autumn and Warring States period, the blade was flat and straight, the sharp angle of the blade was increased, and it was mainly used for chopping, slashing, ruffling, crashing, grating, cutting, washing, stabbing, pressing, stirring, hanging, and clouding. At the end of the Han Dynasty, influenced by the military cavalry, military instruments evolved from the mainstream of the sword to the rise of the sword, and upper-level officials also changed their swords to swords as a distinguished status wear. Hua Weiping (2012) explored the ancient cultural implications and artistic value of swordplay. The study concluded that swordsmanship refers not only to the practical swordplay routines in traditional martial arts, but also to the content of classical literary expressions, including the cultural connotations and unique artistic values given to the sword as a weapon. Swordsmanship and swordsmanship are a form of expression of national emotional catharsis in the development of Chinese culture.

Wang Huafeng research Chinese martial arts Bing Dao Chinese martial arts short arms are divided into two kinds of adult short arms and junior short arms, the weight and length of the two specifications are different, the two colors are divided into red and black, the nature of the competition is divided into individual, team and confrontation, the competition format is divided into single elimination, double elimination and round robin system, Chinese martial arts Bing Dao Chinese martial arts short arms protective gear is divided into shield, chest protection, crotch protection, leg protection, glove; the competition venue is a round practical area; the scoring parts are large and small legs, arms, head, torso; the prohibited parts are brain, crotch, throat, Glove; competition field for the round combat area; scoring parts for the large and small legs, two arms, head, torso; forbidden hit parts back of the head, crotch, throat. The four rituals of standing, holding, squatting and sitting rituals are used as the rituals of the Chinese martial arts short arms program, and the techniques of thrusting, pointing, cutting, crashing, teasing, picking, splitting and chopping are used as the offensive techniques of short arms.

Feng Yale pointed out in the article "The cultural value of Chinese short arms and its development strategy" that: Chinese martial arts Bingdao Chinese martial arts short arms are highly adaptable and have various functional values such as high ornamental and fitness values. In addition, as a traditional Chinese item, the

cultural connotation of Chinese Wushu Bing Dao Chinese Wushu short arms is richer, and the embodiment of etiquette and martial virtue in Chinese Wushu Bing Dao Chinese Wushu short arms is what modern youths need to learn. Long-term systematic practice of Chinese martial arts Bing Dao Chinese martial arts short arms will have a good improvement on physical fitness and mental outlook, and when necessary, it can also defend itself and play a role in self-protection. Chinese martial arts Bing Dao Chinese martial arts short arms has a variety of techniques and practicality. In recent years, the Chinese martial art of Bing Dao Chinese martial art of short arms has sprung to life again, there are signs of recovery, but due to various factors constraints, has not formed a flourishing trend. Compared with the longevity of Western fencing and the rapid development of Japanese kendo, the development of Chinese martial arts short arms deserves deep consideration, and how to inherit and develop this traditional national sport has become an urgent problem.

By reviewing online literature and reading canonical texts, we found that the term "short military" is reflected in modern martial arts textbooks, such as "Chinese Short Military" compiled by Ma Xianda. In fact, it was only after the liberation that the term "short armament" began to be formally recognized and widely used by warriors and writers. After the Cultural Revolution and the reform and opening up of China, with the gradual strengthening of the country's overall national strength and economic and cultural recovery, many abandoned traditional national sports (such as short armament, wrestling, archery, etc.) reappeared in people's eyes after the second or third recovery. However, during this period, there were different developments among different programs in the context of the rise of Western sports and the soil of the native culture. For example, wrestling and archery had a relatively good foundation in the development of Western sports and traditional Chinese culture, so the health of their own soil available for these sports to grow and the possibility that they could be revived twice was greater than other sports. The Chinese martial arts have chosen to develop mainly in the form of routines, and although other combative sports in the Chinese martial arts have achieved various kinds of development, the state and progress of the development of the Chinese martial arts represented by these sports and the degree of attention they have received have not been sufficient so far.

Conclusion

In fact, today, Chinese martial arts Bing Dao Chinese martial arts short arms are not sufficient in either theoretical or technical research, including literature searches within ten or even twenty years of sporadic research. From the state of academic research and practical development, we can see that the development of Chinese martial arts Bing Dao Chinese martial arts short arms is still in a preliminary growth state, or rather a test piece of Chinese martial arts Bing Dao to explore the bright road ahead, Chinese martial arts Bing Dao is still a difficult and far away from maturity and perfection. Therefore, now when we define the Chinese martial arts Bing Dao Chinese martial arts short military project, we generally define the Chinese martial arts Bing Dao Chinese martial arts short military as a modern competitive sport arising from the competitive and scientificization of the Chinese martial arts Bing Jian technology category. It is not a cultural phenomenon that can be summarized by the word "personalized", but a modern sport that is in line with the current development of competitive sports, in line with the needs of human body development, and has clear educational attributes and cultural characteristics. Chinese Martial Arts The Chinese martial art of Bing Dao must represent the Chinese people, and it is full of the cultural connotation and cultural qualities that Chinese martial arts should have. This is our definition of Chinese martial arts Bing Dao Chinese martial arts short arms, rather than defining Chinese martial arts Bing Dao Chinese martial arts short arms in the concept of the so-called killing arts, winning arts and other forms of violence to control violence, defining it in the form of violence-oriented. Such a definition is not only biased, but also does not meet the basic requirements of the state and society for the development of our national sports. In the context of the development of the new era in the 21st century, more emphasis is placed on strengthening the body and on competing as a competitive sport under reasonable rules. The development of Chinese martial arts short arms can only be accepted by more young people in need, or people from different social classes, instead of training themselves to become a "warrior" like in Jin Yong's novels, hiding in the mountains to do the heroic dream of walking in the jungle. The "kill to win" characteristic is no longer applicable and needed in the new era of the 21st century.

Chinese short armament is a Chinese traditional apparatus combat sports, combined with the reality and a lot of research, compared with similar items, Chinese short armament in the development of society is not optimistic, but with the state's attention, policy guidance, related sports colleges began to open short armament course, held every year the national competition, so that the Chinese short armament project in the country is widely developed. Deeply influenced by traditional Chinese Confucianism, the Chinese people's concepts have kept up with the times while still retaining their traditional thinking culture. The traditional Chinese apparatus-based combat confrontation program is the essence of Chinese martial arts, and it contains most of the techniques in traditional Chinese apparatus with a certain degree of aggressiveness. Historically, short arms is a general term for short types of weapons such as swords and knives. Any kind of technical item is the result of the accumulation and summary of the long experience and practice of history. The technique of any instrument is not subjectively made by people, especially the culture accumulated by Chinese 5,000 years of history, which is

summarized by the previous people through all kinds of difficulties. The development of Chinese short armament from the etiquette to the teaching of techniques is liked by today's enthusiasts, and it is easy to see from the national competition held every year that the scale of the competition is gradually growing, the number of competitors is increasing, and the techniques of the competition are improving. The Chinese short arms program is gradually developing in a good way.

As one of the martial arts apparatus items, the development status of Chinese martial arts short armament is not optimistic. The role, value and significance of Chinese martial arts short armament as a Chinese apparatus combat item has an important role in the development history of martial arts apparatus. The current situation of Chinese martial arts short arms research is investigated to find out the shortcomings of Chinese short arms development and put forward the corresponding measures and methods, so that Chinese short arms project can be developed rapidly and play an important role in promoting the development of Chinese martial arts career.

The cultural changes of Chinese martial arts and its inheritance

In summary, there are many studies on Chinese martial arts apparatus hand-to-hand exercises, mostly from the historical and cultural origins, the beauty of martial arts apparatus items, historical combing, analysis and comparison of item techniques, etc. There is no complete detailed elaboration of apparatus combat items as a whole, and there is a lack of promoting and sorting out Chinese short-armed apparatus as a whole, but mostly from individual categories of items. Instead, the study is mostly focused on individual categories, and there is a lack of in-depth discussion on the difficulties faced by the development of equipment combat programs and the solutions to them. Secondly, with the national emphasis on martial arts culture in recent years, the research on Chinese short-armed combat programs has begun to recover, mainly from the issues of program techniques and program promotion, but without analyzing the problems that arise in the promotion of Chinese short-armed combat nowadays; the unified form of Chinese short-armed combat competition, the easy loss of program equipment, the uncertainty of clothing and protective gear, and the lack of unified equipment techniques. Furthermore, the study of Chinese martial arts Bing Dao Chinese martial arts short arms is to make it continue to play an important moral code and value guidance role in contemporary society, that is, to realize the inheritance and development of Chinese martial arts Bing Dao Chinese martial arts short arms culture. The inheritance is to pay tribute to the classics, while the development is to better face the future. As a product of the evolution of ancient society, how to reconstruct and regenerate the Chinese martial arts short arms in the changing history is a subject with important theoretical significance and practical value, however, the research in this area is not available, and the only few literature materials have a weak theoretical foundation, not to mention the construction of a systematic interpretation of the Chinese martial arts short arms culture and modern inheritance and innovation from a macroscopic perspective. The systemic framework of Chinese martial arts is weak, so it is only generalized. However, there are shortcomings in the current research, which need to be further deepened and expanded. From the existing results, scholars' research focuses on the excavation and interpretation of the basic connotation, practical value, and offensive and defensive value of the Chinese martial art of Bingdao Chinese martial art of short arms. As one of China's excellent traditional cultures, Chinese martial arts short arms should be explored and studied in depth in China to promote local culture, take its essence, and contribute to national cultural confidence and strong national sports.

Therefore, combining with the theory of cultural change, taking the cultural confidence of this nation as the starting point, and taking the realization of the inheritance and development of Chinese Wushu Bingdao Chinese Wushu Shorty as the entry point, we propose research questions, determine research objectives, and make logical arguments, so that Chinese Wushu Bingdao Chinese Wushu Shorty can complete a holistic modern reconstruction and benign operation, which has a broad space for exploration and important research value.

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